

RISK FACTORS FOR RECURRENT STROKE

*Salomova N.**Bukhara State Medical Institute,
Department of Traditional Medicine and Occupational Diseases***Abstract**

Each of the pathological conditions is an independent risk factor, but their combined effect several times increases the risk of vascular injury. According to studies, in patients with metabolic syndrome, the volume of body weight increases with age, which is 42-43, 5% in patients over the age of 60 years.

Keywords: repeated strokes, risk, atherosclerosis, arterial hypertension.

The risk factor is a sign that it is pre-morbid and Independent, has a stable probable relationship and is important in predicting it. Risk factor-this is a predictive factor that gives the image of predicting the probability of a disease occurring in an individual and in the population as a whole. Timely detection and correction of risk factors is a promising direction in the Prevention of re – acute violations of cerebral circulation. According to who (2013), about 300 risk factors of stroke have been described, but factors that occur at a high frequency in different populations have a significant impact on the development of the pathological condition and reduce the incidence of their prevention. The combined effect of several risk factors increases the likelihood of developing stroke (according to who (2013), if there are 1-2 factors, the risk of stroke is 6%, 3 factors and more – 19%). Risk factors can be conditionally divided into non-changeable and changeable types. Age, gender, heredity, ethnicity and geography are factors that do not change. The factors that can be changed include diseases caused by harmful habits (tobacco smoking, drug abuse, alcohol consumption, obesity, anemia, depression, psychoemotional stress) and underlying diseases. The main diseases that cause recurrent stroke include arterial hypertension, heart disease, diabetes, atherosclerotic stenosis of the carotid arteries, dyslipidemia. Elderly patients usually have several risk factors, including metabolic disorders and comorbidities. Arterial hypertension is one of the most dangerous factors that provoke the development of stroke. Arterial hypertension is characterized by metabolic changes, changes in the vascular wall, in particular, hemodynamic changes in the system and brain. This is a dangerous factor, which in turn leads not only to re-hemorrhagic, but also to the occurrence of re-ischemic stroke. The prevalence of arterial hypertension in the Russian Federation is 39,2% among men, among women-41,1%. 37,1% of men and 58,9% of women know about their diseases, of which (often not effective enough) 21.6% men and 46.7% women take therapeutic measures. According to the regional-population registry for 2013 year, in Russia, arterial hypertension is recorded in 89,2% of patients with acute disorders of blood circulation in the head brain.

Diastolic arterial blood pressure 105 mm.the sim.top. the risk of developing a stroke is equal to diastolic arterial blood pressure 76 mm.the sim.top. it is 10 times higher than when it is equal to. Thus, patients with primary cerebral stroke belong to a very high risk group, requiring the normalization of blood pressure

and careful selection of antihypertensive drugs. However, a number of studies have shown that the proportion of patients with arterial hypertension with primary and recurrent stroke is approximately the same.

Heart diseases are the causative agent of cardioembolic ischemic stroke, and also one of the main causes of hemodynamic stroke. In angioneurological practice, the introduction of research methods such as Holter monitoring and transthoracic transesophageal echocardiography have made it possible to expand the list of heart diseases that cause head injuries. Nevertheless, the first place will be fibrillation of the limbs (hilpillating arrhythmia), which will cause the occurrence of a cardioembolic subspecies of ischemic stroke. Hilpillating arrhythmia increases the risk of developing stroke by 5 times and increases the mortality rate from this disease by 1.58 times. According to Fremingem studies, hilpillating arrhythmia was recorded in 1.5% of patients in the age group of 50-59 years, and in the age group of 80-89 years-23.5% of cases. Hilpillating arrhythmia is an independent risk factor leading to death among patients who underwent re-radiotherapy and Primary Stroke a month ago. At an older age, sinoatrial node fibrosis and fatty infiltration are one of the causes of an increase in the frequency of fibrillation.

In addition to a violation of the heart rhythm, the cause of cardiac embolism may be other heart diseases that contribute to the formation of a thrombus in its cavity. For patients, acute myocardial infarction, post-infarction cardiac aneurysm, cardiac valve prostheses are also relevant.

Hypercholesterolemia and violation of lipid metabolism (reduction of high-density lipoproteids, an increase in low-density lipoproteids, hypertriglyceridemia) is characterized by the development of atherosclerosis, along with arterial hypertension, which is the main cause of the development of cerebral stroke. The level of cholesterol does not directly depend on age, but increases with the development of metabolic disorders. Komplex, characteristic of the elderly.

The risk of developing an atherothrombotic small type of ischemic stroke is inextricably linked with the degree of narrowing of the cavities of the cerebral arteries. If the development of sleep artery stenosis is more than 75%, the annual risk of a transitory ischemic attack is 13%, if the stroke is 3% and the carotid stenosis is 70-99%, then the risk of developing a stroke is 5-7% per year. With age, several cerebral trunk vessels occlusive atherosclerotic lesions, that is, the frequency of development of the atherogenesis process, increase.

Lesions of multiple trunk vessels in patients over the age of 65 years are three times more common than in single trunk vessel lesions.

Diabetes is an independent risk factor for developing ischemic stroke. Most often, diabetes is not diagnosed in elderly patients who have undergone a stroke, although it can occur in 50% of patients. Usually in such patients, the stroke is severe, a rough violation of carbohydrate metabolism is characterized by a high level of mortality and disability. According to clinical data, threeraydi 5-6 times more likely to ischemic stroke in patients with diabetes than blood transfusions. Acute violations of blood circulation in the head brain do not have a pronounced thrombotic property of a stroke in most patients with diabetes who have experienced an ischemic type, in its development, chronic cerebral vascular insufficiency leading to the slowing of sympathetic vasomotor nerve damage, oxidative processes and hypocapnia. The causes of the development of ischemic thrombotic stroke in patients with diabetes are significant atherosclerotic changes in the blood vessels of the brain, an increase in the viscosity of the blood and a violation of its coagulation properties (inhibition of the anti-coagulation system and the activity of coagulation systems). It was found that depression is directly related to the duration of diabetes in the body, the damage to the vascular system and the protective reactions of resistance. The pathology of the cerebral arteries (carotid and spinal artery) plays an important role in the development of cerebrovascular diseases, which are more associated with atherosclerosis in diabetes mellitus.

Data on the effect of alcohol on the risk of developing stroke of the head remain to this day as the cause of various disagreements. Excessive consumption of alcoholic beverages increases the risk of stroke due to arterial hypertension, hypercoagulant status, a decrease in cerebral blood flow, parasympathetic heart denervation and intermittent fibrillation, which leads to alcohol withdrawal.

In addition, regular consumption of alcohol leads to changes characteristic of the type of toxic encephalopathy. The problem of alcoholism in all patients, etiological causes, risk factors have not yet been adequately studied. At the same time, 5,4-10% of all patients admitted to a psychiatric hospital diagnosed with alcoholism are patients older than 60 years. Young patients often lie in the dispensary and do not receive treatment. Elderly alcoholism is a psychiatric disorder in the third place, noted in patients older than 65 years. The toxic effect of alcohol exacerbates alimentary insufficiency.

Smoking is also an important risk factor for ischemic strokes. However, the direct effect is not proven, most likely it has a multifaceted character. The effect of tobacco as a risk factor for stroke is primarily due to the acceleration of the process of atherosclerosis. Smoking leads to a decrease in the muscle layer of the arteries, which leads to the appearance of arterial hypertension and atherosclerosis. In addition, it was found that in people who smoke tobacco, there is a risk of developing diabetes of the second type.

Hypodynamia and abdominal obesity are an important risk factor for stroke. A number of studies have shown the presence of direct attachment: the more body weight, the higher the risk of developing ischemic stroke. Regular exercise reduces the risk of indirect stroke through a decrease in body weight, a decrease in blood pressure, a decrease in total cholesterol. However, no research has proven that weight loss can lead to a reduction in the risk of recurrent strokes.

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